

METHODS OF MEMORIZING WORDS

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Annotation: The biggest challenge in learning a language of any skill is vocabulary memorization. After all, in this process, you are required to learn not tens or hundreds, but thousands of new words. Your vocabulary is closely related to how well you know the language, and it is also the key to your success in other areas. At this point, it is necessary to mention the word knowledge of monuments for a person who is learning English.

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According to experts, knowledge of 1,200-2,000 words is required for daily communication, regardless of language. So, knowing so many words is enough to communicate freely in English. According to the opinion of experienced pedagogues, it is necessary to know 4,500-5,000 words in order to successfully solve the test questions in the subject of the English language during the entrance exams to the higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan. A student who wants to get a high score in the IELTS exam for admission to foreign universities must know at least 7000 words perfectly. Scientists, writers and poets working in English can use 12,000-15,000 words.

It is clear that, regardless of the purpose and duration of learning English, you definitely need to master a few thousand words. And this does not happen by itself. Have you ever wondered why foreign language learners often find memorizing words difficult and boring? In our opinion, the reason for this is that the methods of memorizing words in the period of learning foreign languages were not so advanced

and convenient. It is no exaggeration to say that there are hundreds of methods and rules for learning new words in a foreign language. We present some of them for you.

Mnemonic

Mnemonics is a set of special methods for expanding memory and remembering the necessary information based on similarity and connection. In this case, new unknown concepts are connected with information already present in the human mind, and as a result, it becomes easier to remember new information. Let's consider an example of this method: it is not always remembered which months of the year have 31 days and which have 30 days. You can easily learn this with the help of the following English poem.

Thirty days have September,
April, June and November,
All the rest have thirty-one;
February has twenty-eight alone,

In addition, mnemonics allow you to use your creativity to make certain information easier to remember.

For example, in English, the word “past” is used in the first 30 minutes when telling the time: 05:20 twenty past five – twenty minutes past five. Now, if you look at a mechanical wristwatch, you will see the hands moving downwards during the first half of each hour. So, when the word low is used in English, the hands of the clock are moving downwards.

In the second half of the hour, the preposition “to” is used in English: 08:43 – seventeen to nine – ten seven kam nine. In this case, we imagine that the arrow that went down until the 30th minute will now go up until the 60th minute. A person who has learned to tell time in this way will probably never forget it. The main idea of this method is to find a way to easily memorize complex information in our brain.

Our brain is adapted to remember pictures, colors, shapes, sounds. Focus on key word method or phonetics The main technique here is the “keyword” technique,

also known as the pronunciation technique. Let's say you think of a word, for example, "a dish". Now you pay attention to how it is pronounced and connect it with the concept of harmony that you know. Then, on the basis of these, you find an unusual idea, place it in a familiar place, and make a sentence about the new concept that has appeared. Bizarre /biza:/ - strange. We associate this word with the Uzbek word for *bozor* (market). We can imagine that our market seemed strange to a foreign visitor, but he kept buying things from the market, saying "this is a bizarre market".

Push /push/. For this word, we choose the Uzbek "Posh-posh!" When we remember the bazaar, we imagine a cart driver pushing a cart there saying "posh-posh". Eminent /eminent/ - famous. It shouldn't be a problem to find a rhymer for this word that you know – singer Eminem. We imagine that when the famous rap singer Eminem sings, the lights go out and it becomes known that he is singing on the phonograph. In a word, Eminent Eminem couldn't sing very well. The method of adaptation to the Uzbek language A student memorizing words in English may face another interesting situation. It is also the fact that some English words are not only in tune with Uzbek words, but also have the same meaning. Of course, there are few words like this, but through effort and research, you can find many such words and increase your vocabulary even more.

Below are examples of such words:

To chop – *chop*

Daddy – *dada*

The wall – *devor*

A voice – *ovoz*

Asphalt – *asfalt*

Galosh – *kalish*

Pistachio – *pista*

Candy – *qand*

Candle – *qandil*

A dish – *idish*

Teachers can develop their students' vocabulary and comprehension by using language that connects to imagery. Teachers can use language that stimulates imagery when lessons include new, essential vocabulary. For example, during a lesson on photosynthesis, asking questions like, "What are you picturing for what the sunlight is doing?" and, "What do you see happening?" During practice time, teachers can use language that prompts students to draw on images. Instead of, "Do you remember the steps of photosynthesis?" teachers can ask, "What are you picturing for photosynthesis?" and "What do you see happening next?" ¹

The art of keeping a dictionary

A dictionary is a tool that every language learner should have. Many people's vocabulary is boring, neglected, and fragmented. Readers don't even think about the fact that this kind of clutter can have a negative effect on remembering new words. Use different colored pens in your vocabulary notebook. The biggest mistake in keeping a dictionary is using the same colored pen. Imagine that all the words in the dictionary are written in blue, they cannot be distinguished from each other, how boring the scene is! After that, the child gets bored of studying. The student's creativity decreases. As a result, our brain does not want to focus on something that is boring.

Learners' perceptions and attitudes towards this strategy:

- The learners had a positive attitude towards the strategy as the notebooks helped them learn English words and increase their word knowledge, particularly of word families.
- They used their notebooks to review the lessons and prepare for the exams.
- Learners preferred making their notebooks in hard copy on paper because they could easily carry them around and review the lessons. ²

Draw pictures in front of the words

Studies show that if you memorize words by placing pictures in front of them, the chances of remembering them increase. In particular, you need to draw pictures

of difficult and vivid new words to remember in your vocabulary. The most important thing is not to draw beautifully, but to draw according to the new word. You should not be ashamed of it. After all, how long will you shy away from useful work?! Also, the picture will revive your photographic memory, if only a little. Use your creativity. Use different patterns and decorate your notebook. When you look at it later, be jealous. At the same time, when memorizing vocabulary, memorizing a vocabulary notebook according to the rules will give you good results. One such rule is to divide words into groups and write them with different pens. You can write verbs with a black pen, nouns with a blue pen, and adjectives with a red pen. Of course, it is your independent choice to write the words in which group in which color.

Make sentences before the words. Forming sentences leads to active memorization of words and does not create difficulty in using them later in other sentences. If it's not difficult, if you also write down fragments of poems and aphorisms, which include new words entering your diary, the result will be even better. As the wise say, "Learning another language is not only learning other words, but also learning to think differently about things." The ability to master these concepts quickly and easily depends on how well we can apply the secrets of word memorization in practice.

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